

This dataset was prepared for the participants in the second championship phase of the Open challenge organized by the CHAIMELEON project for the training of AI models to resolve a specific clinical question related to Lung cancer:

predict overall survival.

All 903 lung cases (images and clinical data) collected until November 2023 were initially taken. Then 3 cases were excluded due to missing death of follow-up information, 11 due to missing CT with the whole thoracic area, and 89 due to missing baseline CT scan.

From the 800 resulting cases, 559 were selected for the training partition and so included in this dataset:

297 event and **262 censored**

The original series (DICOM) with CT scans covering the whole thoracic area were selected, and an extra series was added with harmonized images in NIfTI format.

Only images from diagnosis were included in the dataset.

The complete clinical data is included in the eforms.json file.

The ground truth for the clinical question in that case was the overall survival, calculated as the time elapsed from diagnosis to death or last follow-up. This time can be calculated using the variables:

- "baseline_date": Diagnosis date
- "death_date": Death date, if applicable
- "last_contact_date": Last follow-up date

ID: 5e8a4b13-8c92-40dd-9d4c-04124440f43a

URL: <https://chaimoleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/5e8a4b13-8c92-40dd-9d4c-04124440f43a/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chaimoleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 559

Subjects count: 559

Age range: Between 33 years and 91 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): CHEST, ABDOMEN, LUNG, THORAX / ABDOMEN, THORAX INJECTE, THORAX, SPINE, TAP, WHOLEBODY, HEART, TOTAL BODY, TAP IV, TORAX, CTAP, TC TOTAL BODY, Unknown

Modality: CT, Unknown